

Diabetes Prediction using Machine Learning

Vishnu Raj V
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
vishnurajv20220b@mca.ajce.in

Ankitha Philip
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
ankithaphilip@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Diabetes mellitus, usually known as diabetes, is a metabolic condition characterised by a persistently high level of blood sugar. It is a disorder that arises when the level of blood glucose, commonly known as blood sugar, is abnormally high. Blood glucose is an energy source that comes from the food we eat. The pancreas produces insulin, which aids in the digestion of protein and carbs in food and their conversion to glucose and energy for the body. Insulin is responsible for breaking down glucose and converting it into energy for the body. The body does not always produce enough insulin to work on the glucose. In such circumstances, the glucose is not metabolized and remains in the bloodstream. The presence of a lot of glucose in the blood might lead to chronic health problems over time. Although there is no cure for diabetes, there are steps that may be taken to keep diabetes under control and stay healthy. This research examines the use of machine learning in the prediction and understanding of diabetes in humans.

Keywords— Diabetes prediction analysis, machine learning, KNN Algorithm, logistic regression, report

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a deadly killer that goes unnoticed. It is one of the most feared modern diseases, second only to heart-related ailments in terms of the number of individuals killed. Moreover, the number of diabetics is increasing every day. Diabetic patients are more common than patients with any other condition. Diabetic patients are becoming more prevalent. And the rate of increase is worrying. The problem with diabetes is that it is not detected early on in the disease's progression. Hereditary diabetes and lifestyle-related diabetes are the two main causes of diabetes. Hereditary diabetes is inherited from one's parents. It is passed down through the generations. The poor lifestyle that people adopt is the cause of lifestyle diabetes. In today's fast-paced world, people's lifestyle choices aren't helping them maintain a healthy level of living. Fast food is a major contributor to the growth of diabetes among young people today. Diabetics are a risk factor for a variety of other ailments, including heart disease, kidney problems, nerve damage, stroke, thyroid disease, and so on.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Machine learning's rapid growth has improved its potential for accurate predictive analysis. As a result, a variety of businesses, including the medical field, have adopted its use for a variety of objectives. Machine learning's predictive capacity has improved the precision and speed with which diseases like diabetes are detected

and treated [4]. As a result, a number of studies have been conducted to improve the accuracy of disease prediction and diagnosis using machine learning algorithms.

SVM, RF, Naive Bayes, Kernel Approximation, K-nearest neighbour, and other machine learning classification algorithms have been successfully employed in the diagnosis and management of diabetes. Deep learning algorithms were used in a study [7] to predict the occurrences of diabetes in patients, and they were successful in making the diagnosis with a 95.7 percent accuracy utilizing a unique non-invasive manner.

Furthermore,[7] developed a diabetic mellitus categorization system based on neural networks, with the results indicating that diabetes mellitus can be diagnosed using computational intelligence. Machine learning clearly has the ability to correctly diagnose a variety of diabetes kinds, and the accuracy of the prediction is reliant on the categorization system utilized.

Diabetes prediction is implemented differently in each classification system; as a result, the classification system chosen has an impact on the accuracy of the results. The RF classifier outperforms other prominent classifiers such as Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, and Artificial Neural Networks, according to a study that examined the effectiveness of several classifiers. Furthermore, the design of a classifier's implementation determines its accuracy. Each classifier has advantages and disadvantages, and in order to maximize the power of the widely used classification system, the most efficient algorithms are utilized together to improve the accuracy of the findings.

III. MOTIVATION

Everyone should be concerned about the worrisome rise in the number of diabetic people around the world. Smart computing, in particular, should play a role in predicting, diagnosing, and classifying diabetes in people. This will have a significant impact on medical professionals and medical research in terms of understanding and detecting diabetes in people. The time required for healthcare workers to assess and identify diabetes in people can be dramatically reduced with such a system. This technology can also be used to verify patient data that has been acquired medically.

IV PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The goal of this study is to create a Machine Learning model that can accurately identify whether a patient has diabetes from a given dataset. The model must appropriately classify the dataset into diabetic and non-diabetic categories. The given datasets will be divided into two groups: training and testing. We need to train the model with additional data in the dataset since a dataset with limited data cannot deliver accuracy with learning. The outcomes of these algorithm models can be examined in order to establish a diabetic categorization. If the classification model detects a diabetic entry, the value is set to 1, else it is set to 0. To train to detect diabetes, models such as Logistic Regression, KNN, Random Forest, and gradient boosting classifier will be utilised. These models can utilise a training dataset to predict whether or not a person is diabetic. The following will be the structure of this research:

Figure 1 : Diabetes prediction methodology

The steps are as follows:

1. data collecting
2. data definition
- 3.Pre-Processing

4. Create a model
5. Examine
- 6.Results

We follow the steps below with the algorithm

- 1.Import the libraries first.
2. Add the data to the spreadsheet
3. Establish the dataset
4. Training and testing of data sets
5. Execution of the algorithm
6. Evaluation and comparison of the results

The Pima Indian Diabetes Dataset from the UCI repository is the dataset we used in this investigation. The following is a list of the data in the dataset:

Table 1 : Description of the dataset

S No.	Attributes
1	Pregnancy
2	Glucose
3	Blood Pressure
4	Skin Thickness
5	Insulin
6	BMI (Body Mass Index)
7	Diabetes Pedigree Function
8	Age

The class variable for each attribute in the dataset is the next attribute. This attribute has the values 0 and 1, indicating whether or not the patient has diabetes. The dataset we currently have is unbalanced since only about 500 of the total elements in the dataset are available. Only 268 entries in the dataset are labelled as 1 with positive diabetic entries, meaning that they have no diabetes.

Figure 2: Count of diabetic patients

A. Data Processing: This is the most important step in the machine learning process. The quality of the output generated from the dataset might be harmed by missing data and contaminants in the dataset. Data preparation can be done to improve the effectiveness of the data acquired after the data processing approach has been used. We can perform data preparation on our dataset by using the methods listed below.

1.Removing the missing values – All entries with a value of 0 should be eliminated. Having isn't a valid example. As a result, all entries having a value of 0 must be eliminated. By deleting all of the extraneous elements, we may generate a feature subset.

2.Data Splitting - After the data has been cleaned, it must be normalised for both training and test models. The training data set is utilised to train the algorithm after the split data is ready. Following the training procedure, a training model based on the training features is developed.

B. Machine Learning: After the data is ready, we put the Machine Learning method to the test. To prognosticate diabetes-prone patients, we use a variety of categorization and algorithms. The accuracy of these methods is tested, and the important elements that can assist us in our diabetes prediction are identified. The strategies listed below can be used:

1.Logistic Regression - The most common type of machine learning algorithm is logistic regression. It has a great degree of precision and is usually extremely conclusive. The outcomes of logistic regression are commonly written as 0s and 1s. When data needs to be categorised, it's usually used. In logistic regression, the sigmoid function is used to calculate the likelihood of valid and invalid classes.

$P = 1/1+e-(a+bx)$ Sigmoid function $P = 1/1+e-(a+bx)$
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2.Support Vector Machine (SVM) - This algorithm is also known as Supervised Machine Learning. It makes a hyperplane that divides the various classes. This hyperplane is also used for regression and classifying. It can specify entries in certain classes and classify instances that aren't supported.

Algorithm:

- 1.The hyper plane that best divides the class is chosen.
- 2.The Margin, or the distance between the planes and the data, is determined. This is used to determine which plane is the best.
- 3.The greater the distance between classes, the smaller the likelihood of conception failure.
- 4.We must choose a class with a large margin.
- 5.Margin equals the distance between the negative and positive points.

3. K – Closest Neighbor – The KNN algorithm is another name for it. It's a machine learning algorithm that's supervised. It is based on the notion that things with similar properties stay close together. The concept of a similarity measure is used to classify a new piece of work. It keeps track of the records and categorises them based on their similarity score. To predict a new data point, the algorithm searches the training dataset for the nearest data points. The positive number of closest neighbours is K.

Euclidean distance is used to measure the distance between neighbours. Between two points P and Q, the Euclidean distance is defined as:

Algorithm:

1. A sample dataset is extracted from the Pima Indian Diabetes data set.
2. A data set of attributes and rows is created as a test.
3. The Euclidean distance is calculated using the formula below.
4. A K value is chosen at random.
5. The Euclidean distance and the minimal distance are used to get the nth column of each neighbour.
6. The output values are determined.

If the results are the same, diabetes has been diagnosed; otherwise, the person is not diabetic.

4). Random Forest - This is a machine learning method that may be used to classify and predict data. In comparison to other models, it gets the highest accuracy score. This approach can easily handle any data set of any size. By lowering variance, the Random Forest tree technique can substantially increase the performance of the Decision Tree algorithm. It works by training and outputting the mode of the classes or the regression of the discrete trees while constructing a slew of decision trees.

Algorithm:

1. Total features where RM and select 'R' features from 'M'.
2. Using R features, find the optimal node.
3. Using the best split approach, separate the node into sub nodes.
4. Repeat steps 1-3 until you reach the 'l' number of nodes.
5. Build a forest for "a" number of times to get "n" number of trees by repeating the above procedures.

5).Decision Tree – This is a supervised learning method that may also be used to classify data. It's used to divide the response variable into categories. Its structure is similar to that of a tree. It describes the classification process based on the features provided as input.

Algorithm:

1. Create a tree using the nodes as an input feature.

2. To anticipate the outcome, choose the input feature with the largest information gain.
3. The highest information gain is determined for each feature in each node of the tree.
4. Repeat step 2 to create a subtree with the feature not used in the previous node.

V. BUILD THE MODEL

The development of a model is a crucial step in the diabetes prediction process. In this spell, we put the algorithms we studied earlier into action.

1. The first step is to import the necessary libraries.
2. The diabetes dataset is loaded into the programme.
3. Missing data is deleted during the data pre-processing.
4. In an 8:2 ratio, divide the dataset into training and test data sets.
5. Choose from the following algorithms: Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, KNN, or Support Vector Machine.
6. Create a classifier model based on the chosen algorithm and the training data.
7. Use the test set to evaluate the classifier model.
8. Conduct a comparative evaluation using the performance values acquired for each classifier.
9. Using the performance data obtained, find the algorithm with the best performance.

VI. RESULTS

In order to execute our methods using the Python language, we use a variety of categorization and models. We are seeking for the most accurate machine learning algorithm employing these strategies. When we compare the total performance of each working model, we can observe that the Random Forest classifier outperforms the others.

Figure 3: Results of the test

VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we used a variety of machine learning method

classifiers to predict diabetes from a patient's data set. Using several machine learning methods, we were able to develop various classifier models. We were able to determine the model with the highest accuracy thanks to this research. The Random Forest model was the most accurate of all the models.

VIII. REFERENCES

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